

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN CHRONIC DISEASES AND COMPLICATIONS OF COVID-19 IN HOSPITALIZED PATIENTS

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a lot of irreparable damage to the society, both from the health, social and economic point of view.

This study aims to correlate the complications of COVID-19 with baseline patient characteristics,

The study included 270 patients with covid-19 with concomitant diseases, who were treated in the intensive care unit. **The dead** (107) and the survivors (163).

We used a structured questionnaire form developed by us, which contained information about patients: demographic data, comorbidities, chronic diseases, results of ultrasound, cardiography were studied.

Statistical analysis

- For qualitative data, we calculated frequency and percentage.

The relationship between the factors was determined using Spearman's rank correlation analysis

Results: The main complication was the respiratory system. Most of the patients had acute respiratory failure and bacterial pneumonia. The frequency of respiratory distress was high.

With age older than 65 years, correlates unspecified Shock, renal failure, septic shock, hydrothorax, Artificial lung ventilation.

Hydrothorax shows a reliable positive correlation with such initial factors as, heart failure, prior pulmonary hypertension, heart disease, history of hydrothorax.

Artificial lung ventilation shows a reliable positive correlation with such initial factors as heart failure, History of Pulmonary hypertension, heart disease, History of Hydrothorax

Conclusion:

Complications during covid-19 are related to the patient's initial comorbidities.

Keywords: correlation, comorbid, complication, covid-19.

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused a lot of irreparable damage to the society, both from the health, social and economic point of view.

The main measure that can be taken to prevent and control the unfavorable outcome of the disease is to identify risk factors associated with the prognosis of disease complications and mortality [1].

EEG Abnormalities in COVID-19-Associated Encephalopathy Correlate with Disease Severity EEG abnormalities are common in COVID-19-associated encephalopathy and correlate with disease severity, pre-existing neurological conditions including epilepsy[2].

Hyperglycemia was positively associated with adverse outcomes in COVID-19 patients[3]. Factors contributing to thromboembolic disease in COVID-19 include a combination of immobility, systemic inflammation, platelet activation, endothelial dysfunction, and blood flow stasis, which promote coagulation and thus microvascular and macrovascular thrombosis[4].

This study aims to correlate the complications of COVID-19 with baseline patient characteristics,

Methods: The study included 270 patients with covid-19 with concomitant diseases, who were treated in the intensive care unit. **The dead (107) and the survivors (163).**

We used a structured questionnaire form developed by us, which contained information about patients: demographic data, comorbidities, chronic diseases, results of ultrasound, cardiography were studied.

Statistical analysis

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The clinical material was processed using the program package SPSS 23.

Results:

The initial characteristics of the patients are given in Table 1

Table 1.

Distribution of comorbidities among patients			
Groups	factors	n	%
gender	female	150	55.56
	male	120	44.44
age	< 65	95	65.19
	>65	175	64.81
bad habits	Nicotine	79	29.26
	alcohol	8	2.96
	Drug addiction	1	0.37
Cardiology	heart failure	111	41.11
	Transferred myocardial infarction	58	21.48
	Pulmonary hypertension	51	18.89
	arterial hypertension	239	88.52
	Angina	35	12.96
	heart disease	92	34.07
	Arrhythmia	66	24.44
	Cardiomyopathy	22	8.15
Neurology	fluid in the pericardial cavity	22	8.15
	transferred stroke	32	11.85
	Other neurological pathologies (neuropathy)	4	1.48
	Transient ischemic attack	10	3.70
	severe head injury	3	1.11
	Epilepsy	7	2.59
	dementia	44	16.30
	Alzheimer's	0	0.00
Pulmonology/Physiatrics	transferred pneumonia	64	23.70
	Transmitted TBC	6	2.22
	Phoebe	37	13.70
	Transferred pulmonary artery thromboembolism	4	1.48
	Hydrothorax	63	23.33
	bronchial asthma	2	0.74
	Lung abscess	0	0.00
	Pleurisy	1	0.37
Endocrinology	Diabetes mellitus	85	31.48
	Obesity	28	10.37
	Hypothyroidism or gout	22	8.15
Gastroenterology	Stomach or duodenal ulcer pathology	17	6.30
	Varicose veins of the esophagus	0	0.00
	Gastritis / erosion	24	8.89
	Gallstone disease	6	2.22
	Pancreatitis	0	0.00
Psychiatry	Schizophrenia	1	0.37
	Anxiety Disorders	0	0.00
Hepatology	Hepatitis C	11	4.07
	Hepatitis B	4	1.48
	Chronic liver failure	1	0.37
	cirrhosis of the liver	5	1.85
Angiology	Varicose veins of the blood vessels of the limbs	29	10.74
	Carotid artery occlusion or stenosis	6	2.22
	Aneurysm of the thoracic aorta	0	0.00
	Abdominal aortic aneurysm	3	1.11
Nephrology	Kidney failure	22	8.15
	Bladder disease	4	1.48
	Amyloidosis of the gums	0	0.00

continuation of the table 1.

Distribution of comorbidities among patients			
Groups	factors	n	%
Gastrointestinal tract	stomach, esophagus, intestine	4	1.48
Oncological pathologies	of the brain	1	0.37
	pulmonary/mediastinal	5	1.85
	Liver	1	0.37
	pancreas	2	0.74
	mammary gland	12	4.44
	thyroid gland	2	0.74
	uterus	9	3.33
	prostate	8	2.96
	kidney	0	0.00
	skin and soft tissues	0	0.00
	Oncohematology	2	0.74
	Bladder and urinary tract	0	0.00
Hematology	Anemia	39	14.44
	Coagulopathy	6	2.22

The anamnesis had the highest frequency: heart failure, heart disease and diabetes. Among neurological pathologies, dementia and transferred stroke prevailed, and from pulmonology - transferred pneumonia and hydrothorax. The total share of oncological diseases was small - 40 (15.5%)

Table 2 shows the complications during the treatment period. Complications during treatment.

Table 2.

Complications during the treatment period in intensive care patients with Covid-19.

	n	%
Pulmonary artery thromboembolism	25	9.26
Acute respiratory failure	267	98.89
shock unspecified	33	12.22
Qv. or upper extremity artery embolism	4	1.48
Myocardial infarction	13	4.81
Fluid in the pericardial cavity	13	4.81
pulsatile arrhythmia	1	0.37
Ischemic stroke	9	3.33
Spontaneous hemorrhagic stroke	5	1.85
Liver failure	6	2.22
Kidney failure	31	11.48
Bacterial pneumonia	243	90.00
Sepsis/septic shock	66	24.44
Gastroduodenal bleeding	9	3.33
Hyperglycemia (diabetes mellitus)	8	2.96
Cytokine storm	85	31.48
Urinary tract infection	75	27.78
Pulmonary hypertension	9	3.33
respiratory distress	180	66.67
Anemia	47	17.41
Coagulopathy	14	5.19
Spontaneous pneumothorax	4	1.48
Hydrothorax	86	31.85
emphysema (subcutaneous)	4	1.48
Pneumomediastinitis	4	1.48
encephalopathy (unspecified)	18	6.67
beds	3	1.11
Laryngitis tracheitis	1	0.37
Hematoma of soft tissues developed on the background of anticoagulant	6	2.22

The main complication was the respiratory system. Most of the patients had acute respiratory failure and bacterial pneumonia. The frequency of respiratory distress was high.

Table 3(1).

Correlations between patient comorbidities and complications of Covid-19

		Shock, unspecified	limb artery embolism	myocardial infarction	renal failure	septic shock	gastrointestinal bleeding	Hyperglycemia	Pulmonary hypertension	Anemia
Above 65 years	r	0.134*	0.027	-0.015	0.121*	0.126*	0.008	-0.008	0.051	0.094
	p	0.028	0.665	0.809	0.048	0.038	0.900	0.896	0.405	0.123
Heart failure	r	0.035	0.085	0.236**	0.150*	0.113	0.013	0.166**	0.140*	0.075
	p	0.571	0.163	<0.001	0.014	0.063	0.826	0.006	0.022	0.218
MY history	r	0.028	.162**	0.265**	0.126*	0.111	0.055	0.177**	0.055	-0.047
	p	0.648	0.008	<0.001	0.039	0.069	0.366	0.004	0.366	0.443
Prior pulmonary hypertension	r	0.113	0.099	0.026	0.097	0.110	-0.089	-0.084	0.283**	0.158**
	p	0.065	0.104	0.671	0.113	0.072	0.146	0.171	<0.001	0.010
Prior arterial hypertension	r	0.064	0.044	0.081	0.094	0.041	0.067	-0.005	0.067	-0.018
	p	0.296	0.469	0.184	0.125	0.508	0.272	0.930	0.272	0.770
Heart disease	r	0.044	0.107	0.059	-0.012	0.037	0.042	0.014	0.042	0.126*
	P	0.473	0.080	0.337	0.845	0.547	0.495	0.824	0.495	0.039
Prior Hydrothorax	r	0.091	0.006	<0.001	0.024	0.124*	0.095	0.060	-0.004	.213**
	p	0.135	0.926	0.998	0.700	0.042	0.122	0.326	0.952	<0.001
Prior Renal failure	r	0.012	-0.037	-0.004	0.020	0.053	0.020	-0.052	0.095	0.006
	P	0.839	0.549	0.948	0.747	0.383	0.745	0.393	0.119	0.927

Pulmonary hypertension Reveals a reliable positive correlation with history heart failure and Prior pulmonary hypertension. Age older than 65 correlates with unspecified shock; limb artery embolism correlates with MY history; myocardial infarction correlates with prior renal failure, MY history, renal failure - Above 65 years, prior renal failure, MY history. septic shock - Above 65 years, prior Hydrothorax

Hyperglycemia correlates with heart failure and my history. anemia - heart disease, prior hydrothorax, prior pulmonary hypertension

Table 3(2)

Correlations between patient comorbidities and complications of Covid-19

		Coagulopathy	Hydrothorax	Spontaneous pneumothorax	Artificial lung ventilation
Age over 65 years	r	-0.002	0.218**	0.091	0.235**
	p	0.975	<0.001	0.138	<0.001
heart failure	r	-0.059	0.199**	-0.040	0.211**
	P	0.337	0.001	0.517	<0.001
Hystory of myocardial infarction	r	-0.040	<0.001	-0.064	0.148*
	p	0.518	0.997	0.298	0.015
prior Pulmonary hypertension	r	0.103	0.169**	0.020	0.213**
	p	0.091	0.006	0.741	<0.001
prior arterial hypertension	r	-0.020	0.045	-0.052	0.142*
	P	0.741	0.463	0.397	0.020
prior heart disease	r	0.045	0.122*	-0.088	0.044
	P	0.465	0.045	0.151	0.471
prior Hydrothorax	r	0.070	0.350**	0.079	0.214**
	P	0.249	<0.001	0.199	<0.001
Kidney failure	r	-0.070	0.089	0.075	0.103
	P	0.253	0.146	0.218	0.091

Hydrothorax shows a reliable positive correlation with such initial factors as age over 65 years, heart failure, prior pulmonary hypertension, heart disease, history of hydrothorax.

Artificial lung ventilation shows a reliable positive correlation with such initial factors as Age over 65 years, heart failure, History of Pulmonary hypertension, heart disease, History of Hydrothorax.

Discussion

Elderly patients and patients with chronic comorbidities, such as cardiovascular disease, hypertension,

diabetes, and lung disease, are much more prone to developing severe, critical, and fatal outcomes of COVID-19[5], According to our research, with age older than 65 years, correlates unspecified Shock, renal failure, septic shock, Hydrothorax, Artificial lung ventilation.

Those with chronic pulmonary obstructive disease, congestive heart failure, pulmonary embolism, and prior Pulmonary hypertension are at increased risk to develop or worsen Pulmonary hypertension [6]. This is confirmed by our research.

Conclusion:

Complications during covid are related to the patient's initial comorbidities.

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